

THE GLOBAL STATE OF OPEN ACCESS 2021

REPORT DATE: 08 SEPTEMBER 2022

CENSUS PERIOD: 2020

Summary

At the end of 2021 the global open access level for research published in 2020 reached 49% with an increase of 3% compared to outputs published in 2019. Access provided through publisher websites increased by 3% to 42% for 2019 publications.

GLOBAL OPEN ACCESS LEVELS TREND OVER 11 YEARS FROM 2010 TO 2020

Access through other platforms was 21% in 2020 with no growth compared to 2019 publications. This may be the result of embargos depressing rates of access through repositories for the most recent years of publication. Zero-embargo access through non-publisher platforms for 2020 was 32% of all outputs available through other platforms. Future reports will track the evolution of immediate other platform open access over time.

Open Access by Country

The countries with the highest levels of open access continue to be countries with small publication output numbers, with Indonesia and Brazil dominating amongst countries with more than 10,000 outputs in 2020 with a set of European countries following. European countries tend to show higher levels of open access through other platforms, compared to other countries with high levels of accessibility and this is in part due to generally shorter embargos, particularly in north-western Europe.

TOP 10 COUNTRIES BY OPEN ACCESS LEVELS

DATA OVER 11 YEARS FROM 2010 TO 2020

Methodology

The primary data table used was the final DOI table in the Academic Observatory for 2021, `bigquery://academic-observatory.observatory.doi20211211`. Open Access types and the analysis for categorising them from Unpaywall are as described on the [COKI Open Access Dashboard](#).

This report was generated automatically from the source data on 08 September 2022 and the relevant code and state of the repository is available [on github](#):

- Commit hash: `f1d3eaa8e49793511be4573298bb664040b10d17`
- Branch: `main`